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Properties and structural performance of KD-II SiC fiber with different temperature in air and argon atmosphere

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1 Introduction

1.Introduction

SiC fibers have aroused great interests for their use as reinforcement materials for high-temperature ceramic composites, due to their knittability, temperature resistance and mechanical tensile strength.

Development

Stage 1. In the early stage of development, American researchers used chemical vapor deposition (CVD) methods to deposit SiC on tungsten and carbon fiber (CF) surfaces respectively, and the diameter of the fibers reaches 100 micrometer or more, which can not be used to weave prefabricated technology.

Stage 2. In the late 1970s, professor Yajima from Japan initiated polymer pyrolysis method to prepare continuous SiC fibre, and the diameter is less than 15 micrometer with good weaving ability. This result has laid a technical foundation for the industrial production of SiC fibers and has greatly promoted the extensive research and application of SiCf/SiC.

Stage 3. Since 1980, Japanese enterprises have adopted the polymer pyrolysis method to produce fiber with a diameter of about 10 mm, and achieved industrial production. This has formed various shapes of SiC fabric and has become the mainstream of research and development of SiC fiber composites.

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Experimental procedure

2. Experimental procedure

3

Results and analysis

3. Results and analysis

untreated

800 °C for 1h in air

1000 °C for 1h in air

1200 °C for 1h in air

1400 °C for 1h in air

1500 °C for 1h in air

3. Results and analysis

Fig.2 Surface morphology of SiC fibers without heat treatment

3. Results and analysis

Fig.3 Surface morphology of SiC fibers with heat treatment at 1500°C in different atmosphere :(a) air; (b) argon

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Summary

4. Summary

The high temperature exposure for KD-II continuous silicon carbide fibers was carried out at 800 °C, 1000 °C, 1200 °C, 1400 °C and 1500 °C for 1 h in air and argon atmosphere. Conclude as follows:

1. XRD results showed that strong peaks from silica oxide could be observed when temperature exceeded 1400°C, indicating that the silica oxide began to crystallize on the surface of the fiber. However, no silica formation was observed from XRD results for different temperature heat treatment in argon atmosphere.
2. SEM micrographs revealed that the silica oxide layer was formed on the surface of SiC fiber at 1500°C in air and the crack of the silica oxide layer was observed. But in argon atmosphere, the smooth surface was observed at all temperatures, suggesting that the formation of silica was prevented due to the presence of argon. From the above analysis, it can be seen that the surface structure of SiC fibers is significantly changed at high temperature in air .

Thank you